

Design, synthesis, anti-cancer screening and structure activity relationship studies of biphenyl linked fused imidazoles

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Biphenyl is a privileged scaffold observed in several marketed drugs and is known to predominantly bind to a wide range of proteins with high specificity. Fused imidazole is another privileged structure which is found in several bioactive compounds. The present investigation describes the design and synthesis of a biprivileged compound library comprising biphenyl linked fused imidazoles and their activity against NCI-60 cell line to identify potential 'hits' for further anti-cancer drug discovery. In the preliminary investigation, imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine based heterocycles having *tert*-alkyl amine and a biphenyl substituent demonstrated promising results against some of the leukaemia, colon cancer, ovarian cancer as well as breast cancer cell lines. The active compounds were also found to be non-toxic to several other cancer cell lines, warranting further structure activity relationship (SAR) investigation. A systematic structural modifications and bioactivity evaluation against NC-I60 cell line resulted in the identification of 2-aryl-*N*-(2,4,4-trimethylpentan-2-yl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyrazin-3-amine scaffold with biphenyl, benzo[d][1,3]dioxole and 4-(trifluoromethyl)benzene as substituents at C-2 position showing anticancer activity.

Keywords: NCI-60, privileged scaffold, fused imidazoles, biphenyl, GBB MCR, SAR.

Introduction

Aromatic heterocyclic scaffolds exist in a wide range of natural products and are being frequently used to probe and understand various biologically significant pathways¹. In drug discovery process, functionalized aromatic compounds are dominated by their ability to make interactions with hydrophobic residues, polar amide/hydroxyl groups, and charged moieties present in various biomacromolecules. Among such aromatic scaffolds, biphenyl is a privileged structure which comprises 4.3% of the marketed drugs and is present in several bioactive heterocycles². Losartan and valsartan are the

top selling drugs which contain the biphenyl scaffold³. Biphenyl containing molecules are also known to have potential anti-malarial, anti-microbial, anti-hypertensive as well as anti-atherosclerotic activities⁴. Fesik *et al.* found that the biphenyl containing heterocycles predominantly bind to a wide range of proteins with high specificity^{2a}. Very recently, Yang *et al.* designed novel oxime-biphenyl-diarylpyrimidines utilizing a privileged scaffold inspired strategy having potential to treat HIV-1⁵. Due to the flexible nature of the biphenyl scaffold, it can be accommodated into a wide range of enzyme/protein pockets and show favorable interactions with

the receptors. Honokiol (**1**), a natural product comprising a biphenyl scaffold, extracted from the bark of *Magnolia officinalis* exhibits antitumor activity against several cancer cells including colorectal cancer, prostate cancer, leukaemia, and melanoma (Fig. 1)⁶. Biphenyl skeleton is also observed in several other cytotoxic natural products such as eupomatilone-6⁷ (**2**), allocolchicine⁸ (**3**) and buflavine⁹ (**4**). MP5-F9¹⁰ (**5**), the natural product combretastatin A4 (microtubule targeting agent) inspired designed hit also showed anticancer activity via mitotic arrest. Whereas, the nitro-vinyl biphenyl derivative (**6**) showed cytotoxicity in nanomolar range against Hela and MCF-7 cell lines¹⁰.

Hybridization of two different moieties that are biologically active could result in new scaffolds with improved physicochemical as well as pharmacological properties. This approach can easily provide novel scaffolds targeting significant biological pathways. Fused imidazole based scaffold is one of such important privileged structure which was found in several marketed drugs such as Zolpidem (treatment of insomnia), minodronic acid (treatment of osteoporosis), soraprazan, alpedim (treatment of anxiety), zolmidine etc.¹¹. Substituted fused imidazole **7** is protein-E (CENP) targeting anticancer agent currently available in the market¹².

Similarly, compounds **8** and **9** are the imidazo[2,1-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazole analogues of anticancer drug levamisole showing promising results¹³. Based upon the above-mentioned attributes of biphenyl and fused imidazoles, we planned to directly link biphenyl scaffold with imidazole fused pyridine/pyrazine and thiazole skeleton and evaluated their potential against a panel of NCI-60 cancer cell lines.

Results and discussion

Greobke-Blackburn-Bienaymé (GBB) multicomponent reaction is a one-pot protocol where an amidine, aldehyde and isonitrile reacts together to generate diverse compounds containing imidazole fused heterocycles¹⁴. Following this strategy we sought to design biphenyl linked fused imidazoles were synthesized (Fig. 2) via GBB reaction which was carried out in acetonitrile using HCl as a catalyst to generate the desired compounds in 50–90% yields (Scheme 1). All the products were purified through column chromatography using 230–400 mesh silica gel and characterized by NMR and HRMS analysis. The purity of these compounds was determined by HPLC.

Fig. 1. Design of biphenyl linked fused imidazoles.

	Cell Line	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
Leukemia	CCRF-CEM	33.68	15.95	40.78	18.00	27.11	22.69	18.81	4.66	68.27
Leukemia	HL-60(TB)	42.25	21.30	39.40	30.28	7.12	0.00	17.73	1.32	78.73
Leukemia	K-562	71.27	44.80	44.63	43.35	37.26	11.88	57.69	16.82	15.39
Leukemia	MOLT-4	30.71	32.75	52.61	37.53	37.47	30.14	12.69	15.83	41.65
Leukemia	RPMI-8226	42.93	29.75	39.69	42.48	31.30	36.09	21.66	7.09	55.85
Leukemia	SR	58.39	31.13		42.37			44.08	20.47	
NSCLC	A549/ATCC	18.90	9.66	24.29	12.69	43.57	11.55	7.21	10.35	30.41
NSCLC	EKVX	38.74	34.50	10.69	30.71	7.30	6.56	30.22	39.74	3.10
NSCLC	HOP-62	22.42	11.25	16.01	18.12	20.06	27.31	8.12	0.00	29.05
NSCLC	HOP-92	11.82	26.01	34.26	24.17	6.65	15.93	6.26	13.71	15.46
NSCLC	NCI-H226	22.38	11.36	7.12	16.42	12.65	10.17	30.62	3.30	14.72
NSCLC	NCI-H23	35.22	16.49	12.03	8.84	8.49	11.17	20.92	6.52	3.18
NSCLC	NCI-H322M	20.30	8.82	11.86	0.71	18.48	18.06	22.03	9.00	23.59
NSCLC	NCI-H460	20.24	12.68	18.82	10.45	19.97	1.06	11.43	10.18	12.99
NSCLC	NCI-H522	49.59	24.42	23.14	26.59	62.52	15.78	26.23	16.84	61.89
Colon Cancer	COLO 205	26.09	6.44		0.00			0.00	0.00	
Colon Cancer	HCC-2998	19.34	20.71	3.99	1.70	6.35	0.00	0.00	8.42	0.68
Colon Cancer	HCT-116	46.55	21.97	33.23	35.85	40.18	16.85	19.74	11.39	24.98
Colon Cancer	HCT-15	48.36	33.06	8.25	27.58	15.48	2.09	23.33	18.46	6.98
Colon Cancer	HT29	83.31	39.39	21.10	32.49	69.46	9.57	44.48	15.05	13.76
Colon Cancer	KM12	42.07	17.68	9.95	12.61	20.10	0.00	18.30	6.93	10.38
Colon Cancer	SW-620	6.77	5.29	10.49	0.00	2.89	3.36	0.39	0.00	4.33
CNS Cancer	SF-268	10.63	4.55	14.77	0.99	18.52	3.08	3.98	1.69	28.46
CNS Cancer	SF-295	29.22	0.00	4.53	21.16	2.43	3.97	11.23	0.00	1.10
CNS Cancer	SF-539	6.17	0.00	2.54	14.26	9.49	12.13	2.18	0.15	7.44
CNS Cancer	SNB-19	14.04	15.78	2.34	16.30	5.68	2.56	13.28	8.95	9.36
CNS Cancer	SNB-75		0.00	19.33	4.69	11.30	20.26		1.44	22.82
CNS Cancer	U251	18.79	11.06	11.16	12.15	40.33	3.34	7.13	6.51	27.59
Melanoma	LOX IMVI	22.34	0.00	3.74	8.41	2.79	0.00	9.66	0.00	5.35
Melanoma	MALME-3M	8.59	14.94	10.26	25.19	0.00	6.74	4.76	3.82	0.97
Melanoma	M14	29.08	0.00	12.38	7.11	10.75	7.10	21.03	11.20	17.43
Melanoma	MDA-MB-435	18.13	0.00	10.63	4.33	17.25	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.04
Melanoma	SK-MEL-2	21.83	5.87	9.32	5.06	27.81	7.12	22.48	0.00	11.36
Melanoma	SK-MEL-28	5.93	6.67	4.91	6.58	0.00	4.07	0.00	0.00	0.81
Melanoma	SK-MEL-5	32.92	13.06	10.09	26.47	0.00	8.69	20.70	3.26	0.00
Melanoma	UACC-257	17.49	0.00	3.30	2.77	16.71	0.73	6.45	0.00	10.29
Melanoma	UACC-62	32.43	18.26	6.29	22.14	24.13	9.29	13.28	12.17	7.48
Ovarian Cancer	IGROV1	14.81	36.81	7.52	17.71	33.99	9.27	8.71	32.81	8.11
Ovarian Cancer	OVCAR-3	26.70	23.76	17.42	12.62	9.85	0.00	7.56	8.58	23.61
Ovarian Cancer	OVCAR-4	41.47	32.15	18.47	31.84	100.00		8.39	13.38	16.84
Ovarian Cancer	OVCAR-5	8.76	6.61	18.79	10.42	11.90	22.65	1.17	11.82	11.82
Ovarian Cancer	OVCAR-8	9.48	9.34	23.39	12.14	29.79	16.66	0.00	5.15	30.51
Ovarian Cancer	NCI/ADR-RES	17.74	18.26	5.31	22.91	2.31	4.74	4.82	10.51	2.61
Ovarian Cancer	SK-OV-3	19.11	19.90	23.47	18.35	23.69	20.23	5.42	17.33	16.63
Renal Cancer	786-0	14.51	2.21	9.71	13.00	19.35	4.85	0.00	0.73	54.43
Renal Cancer	A498	38.47	10.15	21.32	22.28	24.09	3.30	15.54	0.00	9.00
Renal Cancer	ACHN	12.66	9.30	2.00	6.62	0.00	5.85	10.05	2.83	7.20
Renal Cancer	CAKI-1	33.12	34.59	15.60	20.22	23.89	16.70	25.76	28.72	27.59
Renal Cancer	RXF 393	23.50		8.34		5.57	0.27	15.24		9.85
Renal Cancer	SN12C	23.75	16.22	9.50	22.86	1.27	3.76	19.84	6.37	16.93
Renal Cancer	TK-10	12.07	10.72	4.71	1.78	13.37	0.00	0.00	8.73	0.00
Renal Cancer	UO-31	38.36	43.53	35.59	27.63	31.22	30.21	26.23	32.04	55.77
Prostate Cancer	PC-3	31.87	47.08	37.31	13.06	34.62	17.49	9.72	21.92	33.92
Prostate Cancer	DU-145	18.71	2.60	19.84	7.66	5.09	4.39	9.27	0.00	7.46
Breast Cancer	MCF7	54.43	55.66	21.34	21.09	17.68	8.05	41.07	46.96	28.20
Breast Cancer	MDA-MB-231	9.93	10.99	21.21	15.46	9.42	18.82	9.51	10.25	16.88
Breast Cancer	HS 578T	0.00	0.00	13.72	0.00	4.49	10.05	3.31	0.00	12.39
Breast Cancer	BT-549	23.72	4.91	18.22	24.66	4.99	10.87	0.00	7.62	48.35
Breast Cancer	T-47D	69.29	47.07		51.41			50.28	48.22	
Breast Cancer	MDA-MB-468		12.14	21.40	23.24	0.00	0.00		0.00	15.40

Fig. 2. Heatmap of NCI-60 cell line screening for compounds 10-18.

The anticancer potential of the synthesized analogues (10-18) was evaluated against NCI-60 cancer cell line panel¹⁵.

The diverse cell line panel provide a unique platform to compare tested compounds by their effect patterns and identify

potential 'hits' for further drug discovery¹⁶. The synthesized library of compounds were screened against the NCI-60 cell line panel at a single dose (10 μ M). The output was processed and reported as percentage (%) inhibition heatmap (Fig. 2).

The compounds **10**, **14** and **18**, which are placed diagonally in Scheme 1 showed promising activities. Specifically, the imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine-based compound **10** having *tert*-butyl amine and a privileged biphenyl substituent demonstrated substantial inhibition of leukaemia cell lines K-562 (71% inhibition) and SR (58% inhibition). Compound **10** was also found to be active against colon cancer cell line HT29 (83% inhibition) as well as breast cancer cell line T-47D (69% inhibition). The structurally similar analogue having *tert*-octylamine substituent on the imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine hetero-

cycle (**14**) was observed to be selectively toxic to the colon cancer cell line HT29 (69% inhibition) and was also found to be active against non-small cell lung cancer cell line H522 (62% inhibition). It was noteworthy to observe that the compound **14** completely inhibited the growth of the ovarian cancer cell line OVCAR-4 at 10 μ M concentration. Among the initial small set of compounds, the biphenyl linked imidazo[2,1-*b*]thiazole **18** having 2-morpholinoethyl amine substituent was another active analogue showing potential anticancer activity against leukemia CCRF-CEM, HL-60 as well as non-small cell lung cancer cell line H522 with more than 60% inhibition at the tested concentration. The three active compounds as well as the other analogues were found to be non-toxic to several other cell lines and also a clear relationship between the substituents and the observed ac-

Scheme 1. A diverse set of biphenyl linked fused imidazole.

tivity was observed which demanded further structure activity relationship (SAR) investigation.

To increase the diversity of the synthesized library and to further understand the SAR, dealkylation of the preliminary 'hit' (compound **14**) with imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyrazine scaffold was carried out to observe the effect of the free amino functionality on the anticancer activity (Scheme 2). The dealkylation reaction was executed in the presence of 1:1 mixture of CF₃COOH and CH₂Cl₂ at room temperature to generate the primary amine product **19** in 90% yield.

Scheme 2. Dealkylation of HIT compound **14**.

Complete loss of anticancer activity by compound **19** against all the cancer cell lines tested confirmed the importance of the *tert*-alkyl substituent in this scaffold. Further, some more analogues of the compound **14** were synthesized using similar GBB reaction condition (Scheme 3). The imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyrazine with 2-octylamino substituents were kept constant and various aldehydes were selected instead

of biphenyl-4-carboxaldehyde so as to understand the appropriate structural requirements at C-2 position of the heterocycle for improved anticancer activity.

In particular, the compound **20** was synthesized to check the importance of the biphenyl moiety in the 'hit' scaffold **14**. Further, the phenyl group was replaced with pyridyl functionality and both 3-pyridinecarboxaldehyde as well as 4-pyridinecarboxaldehyde were selected to synthesize analogues **21** and **22**, respectively. It was important to observe that the analogues **20**, **21** as well as **22** did not show any prominent inhibition of any of the cancer cell line tested (Fig. 3). The compound **23** with benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxole substitution instead of a biphenyl group, inhibited 94% of the colon cancer cell line (HCT-116) at 10 μM whereas the structurally related 3-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzene substituted compound **24** was found to bereft of any anticancer activity. Interestingly, the 4-(trifluoromethyl)benzene substituted compound **25** showed complete inhibition (100% inhibition) of colon cancer cell line (HCT-116), melanoma cell line (M14) as well as renal cancer cell line (786-0). Further modification in this series with 3-benzonitrile substituent resulted in compound **26** with complete loss of the anticancer activity. Overall, the present investigation resulted in the discovery of 2-aryl-*N*-(2,4,4-trimethylpentan-2-yl)imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyrazin-3-amine

Scheme 3. Further optimization of HIT compound **14**.

	Cell Line	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26
Leukemia	CCRF-CEM	35.27	4.09	0.00	8.37	10.91	19.92	14.23	13.79
Leukemia	HI-60(TR)	39.17	4.08	0.00	0.00	77.16	73.69	70.64	15.31
Leukemia	K-562	20.11	6.01	2.21	1.65	28.02	19.51	34.45	29.14
Leukemia	MOLT-4	15.86	9.96	3.62	5.93	30.64	30.52	31.50	27.36
Leukemia	RPMI-8226	13.00	14.95	11.96		30.29		37.10	
Leukemia	SR	16.58	18.54	5.43		26.89		40.24	
NSCLC	A549/ATCC	9.59	9.64	3.92	3.64	17.26	12.69	16.90	18.09
NSCLC	FKVX	7.93	8.92	9.95	6.91	19.67	6.64	20.62	18.95
NSCLC	HOP-62	4.95	2.37	0.00	0.00	2.06	0.00	7.26	4.01
NSCLC	HOP-92	0.00	26.19	5.87	12.91	29.74	7.31	17.41	33.71
NSCLC	NCI-H226	3.70	3.34	4.21	9.75	9.91	14.53	7.49	9.59
NSCLC	NCI-H23	3.88	0.00	3.93	0.76	2.30	3.28	17.59	0.00
NSCLC	NCI-H322M	3.33	1.29	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.77
NSCLC	NCI-H460	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.80	0.91	10.51	3.46
NSCLC	NCI-H522	19.49	17.93	13.76	12.94	25.86	18.41	32.55	25.50
Colon Cancer	COLO 205	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.54	4.04	11.19
Colon Cancer	HCC-2998	0.66	1.03	0.00	0.00	6.26	0.00	7.90	0.00
Colon Cancer	HCT-116	3.56	9.59	10.06	9.88	94.64	14.44	100.00	31.35
Colon Cancer	HCT-15	4.61	4.28	1.65	2.06	15.91	11.54	26.15	15.74
Colon Cancer	HT29	5.35	8.94	5.50	6.99	20.04	0.00	42.59	10.40
Colon Cancer	KM12	2.53	0.76	0.00	1.90	3.80	0.37	16.21	5.23
Colon Cancer	SW-620	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.59
CNS Cancer	SF-268	8.89	11.23	4.51	1.43	15.88	18.24	11.16	7.61
CNS Cancer	SF-295	7.23	4.09	4.13	0.00	13.76	7.90	13.73	14.83
CNS Cancer	SF-539	8.10	9.46	9.53	6.18	8.50	16.04	14.03	7.46
CNS Cancer	SNB-19	8.67	7.94	4.60	2.70	9.15	7.77	8.21	9.97
CNS Cancer	SNB-75	0.00	13.49	5.57	19.56	32.50	49.31	18.93	32.52
CNS Cancer	U251	4.67	4.90	8.42	0.81	4.39	10.24	6.98	12.00
Melanoma	LOX IMVI	0.88	0.00	6.08	1.21	5.96	1.21	2.40	6.64
Melanoma	MALME-3M	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	13.28	0.00	0.00
Melanoma	M14	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	54.09	15.25	100.00	0.00
Melanoma	MDA-MB-435	10.02	0.00	0.00	0.80	0.91	15.57	1.25	1.67
Melanoma	SK-MEL-2	3.51	1.93	1.56	0.00	4.44	0.00	8.97	0.00
Melanoma	SK-MEL-28	6.58	0.00	1.46	0.00	5.66	22.07	6.11	0.00
Melanoma	SK-MEL-5	6.62	3.73	3.29	0.63	12.28	9.10	9.97	8.55
Melanoma	UACC-257	2.49	0.53	0.42	0.00	0.00	12.08	1.35	2.54
Melanoma	UACC-62	5.79	19.86	4.72	7.09	34.02	22.21	27.14	33.53
Ovarian Cancer	IGROV1	0.00	10.31	0.09	0.21	27.86	9.07	32.58	7.96
Ovarian Cancer	OVCAR-3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	7.53	0.50	15.23	1.29
Ovarian Cancer	OVCAR-4	3.72	9.76	3.93	15.99	13.12	13.20	20.58	16.31
Ovarian Cancer	OVCAR-5	2.00	9.42	6.37	6.28	8.77	0.38	0.00	0.93
Ovarian Cancer	OVCAR-8	2.68	5.57	0.00	4.45	4.95	5.36	10.82	13.64
Ovarian Cancer	NCI/ADR-RES	1.36	7.30	9.36	0.46	12.32	6.99	18.11	10.84
Ovarian Cancer	SK-OV-3	0.00	8.82	0.00	7.19	8.04	0.00	17.34	4.58
Renal Cancer	786-0	12.93	5.38	4.23	3.43	32.28	2.32	100.00	13.15
Renal Cancer	A498	11.39	15.05	9.67	9.11	24.40	15.09	16.25	34.38
Renal Cancer	ACHN	0.79	4.80	6.89	12.35	13.51	9.97	12.98	12.67
Renal Cancer	CAKI-1	11.96	20.00	12.66	19.41	30.43	21.77	24.63	30.04
Renal Cancer	RXF 393				6.21		11.95		9.54
Renal Cancer	SN12C	10.91	6.29	2.53	0.00	7.18	8.16	13.92	2.67
Renal Cancer	TK-10	0.23	0.07	0.00	0.76	1.67	0.00	0.00	3.55
Renal Cancer	UO-31	16.26	28.96	20.27	13.28	36.86	29.20	35.85	29.11
Prostate Cancer	PC-3	2.30	21.12	3.93	2.32	32.98	10.79	31.52	16.58
Prostate Cancer	DU-145	2.24	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	7.01	4.61
Breast Cancer	MCF7	11.31	6.50	4.36	3.45	25.91	24.20	33.54	16.67
Breast Cancer	MDA-MB-231	0.00	4.23	13.26	5.05	16.10	10.24	13.98	16.68
Breast Cancer	HS 578T	0.00	5.26	0.00	7.80	11.46	5.56	0.00	8.84
Breast Cancer	BT-549	8.57	10.51	10.26	1.37	17.82	12.92	24.05	5.10
Breast Cancer	T-47D	11.69	10.17	8.36	13.89	15.84	7.66	25.64	9.28
Breast Cancer	MDA-MB-468	2.30	0.00	7.95	12.50	4.78	5.78	0.00	1.14

Fig. 3. Heatmap of NCI-60 cell line screening for compounds 19-26.

scaffold with biphenyl, benzo[d][1,3]dioxole and 4-(trifluoromethyl)benzene as prominent aryl substituents at C-2 position showing prominent anticancer activity.

Conclusions

In this study, a set of compounds based on a privileged molecular scaffold comprising biphenyl linked fused imidazoles were synthesized via GBB-MCR methodology and screened through NCI-60 cancer cell line panel for their anti-cancer activity. Preliminary screening (at a single dose of 10 μ M), furnished compound **10** which showed substantial inhibition of leukaemia cell line (K-562, 71% inhibition; SR, 58% inhibition), colon cancer cell line (HT29, 83% inhibition) as well as breast cancer cell line (T-47D, 69% inhibition). The structurally similar analogue **14** completely inhibited the growth of the ovarian cancer cell line OVCAR-4 at 10 μ M concentration. Further SAR investigation, confirmed the important role of C-3 *tert*-alkyl amino as well as biphenyl substituent at the C-2 position on the imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyrazine scaffold. Compound **19** without *tert*-alkyl substituent as well as the analogues synthesized by the replacement of biphenyl group with phenyl (**20**), pyridyl (**21**, **22**) and a few more substituted phenyl analogues (**24**, **26**) were observed to be relatively less active. Interestingly, the compound **23** with benzo[d][1,3]dioxole substitution instead of a biphenyl group, inhibited 94% of the colon cancer cell line (HCT-116) at 10 μ M whereas the 4-(trifluoromethyl)benzene substituted compound **25** showed complete inhibition of colon cancer cell line (HCT-116), melanoma cell line (M14) as well as renal cancer cell line (786-0).

Experimental

General procedure for the synthesis of compounds (10-18) and (20-26): To a solution of 2-amidine (1.59 mmol) and aldehyde (3.18 mmol) in anhydrous acetonitrile (5 mL), isonitrile (1.59 mmol) was added followed by the addition of 4 N HCl/dioxane (5 μ L) at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then allowed to react under microwave irradiation at 110°C for 20 min. After the completion of reaction (monitored by TLC), the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the crude mixture obtained was purified using flash column chromatography to yield the target compounds (**10-18** and **20-26**) in 50–90% yield.

2-([1,1'-Biphenyl]-4-yl)-N-(2,4,4-trimethylpentan-2-yl)imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyrazin-3-amine (14**):** Yield 70%; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 9.01 (d, *J* 1.3 Hz, 1H), 8.15 (dd, *J* 4.6, 1.4 Hz, 1H), 7.97–7.94 (m, 2H), 7.87 (d, *J* 4.6 Hz, 1H), 7.74–7.70 (m, 2H), 7.69–7.66 (m, 2H), 7.48–7.45 (m, 2H), 7.38–7.35 (m, 1H), 1.61 (s, 2H), 1.05 (s, 9H), 1.00 (s, 6H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 143.5, 142.4, 140.9, 140.7, 137.5, 133.5, 129.0, 128.9, 128.9, 127.6, 127.3, 127.2, 125.2, 116.6, 61.5, 57.2, 31.9, 31.9, 29.3; HRMS *m/z*: calculated for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{31}\text{N}_4^+$ [$\text{M}+\text{H}$] $^+$ 399.25432, found 399.25505.

2-(4-(Trifluoromethyl)phenyl)-N-(2,4,4-trimethylpentan-2-yl)imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyrazin-3-amine (25**):** Yield 80%; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (598 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$): δ 8.97 (d, *J* 1.3 Hz, 1H), 8.45 (dd, *J* 4.7, 1.3 Hz, 1H), 8.37 (d, *J* 8.2 Hz, 2H), 7.89 (d, *J* 4.7 Hz, 1H), 7.79 (d, *J* 8.3 Hz, 2H), 4.74 (s, 1H), 1.58 (s, 2H), 0.95 (s, 9H), 0.93 (s, 6H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (150 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$): δ 142.9, 139.1, 138.8, 136.8, 128.6, 128.5, 127.9, 127.6, 126.2, 125.8, 125.2, 124.9, 124.9, 123.4, 117.5, 60.6, 55.8, 31.5, 31.2, 28.6; HRMS *m/z*: calculated for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{F}_3\text{N}_4^+$ [$\text{M}+\text{H}$] $^+$ 391.21041, found 391.21114.

Procedure for the synthesis of 2-([1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl)imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyrazin-3-amine (19**):** To a solution of compound **14** (100 mg, 0.25 mmol) in anhydrous CH_2Cl_2 (1 mL), trifluoroacetic acid (1 mL) was added and the final reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 20 min. After the completion of reaction, trifluoroacetic acid was neutralized with saturated aqueous solution of NaHCO_3 (50 ml) and formed compound was extracted in dichloromethane. The organic layer was collected, dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and concentrated to obtain a crude residue, which was purified using column chromatography to obtain product **19** in 90% yield; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (500 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$): δ 8.82 (d, *J* 1.4 Hz, 1H), 8.28 (dd, *J* 4.7, 1.4 Hz, 1H), 8.17–8.08 (m, 2H), 7.75 (ddt, *J* 8.2, 6.3, 1.5 Hz, 5H), 7.52–7.44 (m, 2H), 7.40–7.31 (m, 1H), 5.89 (s, 2H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (126 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$): δ 142.2, 139.8, 138.3, 134.1, 133.4, 129.0, 128.0, 127.8, 127.4, 126.9, 126.7, 126.5, 115.1; HRMS *m/z*: calculated for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_4^+$ [$\text{M}+\text{H}$] $^+$ 287.12912, found 287.12808.

NCI-60 Screening methodology:

Growth inhibition experiments were performed at the US National Cancer Institute (NCI) according to the method as described by Boyd and Paull^{15a}.

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Supporting Information

The Supporting Information (analytical data, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, HRMS, and HPLC spectra of all the synthesized compounds) is available at www.indianchemicalsociety.com.

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